

THE ROLE OF NATIONAL VALUES IN SHAPING THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF STUDENT YOUTH

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Abstract: The article addresses the issue of the spiritual and moral upbringing of youth, along with emphasizing the role and significance of national values in shaping the spiritual and moral education of student youth. The definitions provided are based on scientific foundations, exploring the place and importance of "The Role of National Values in Shaping the Spiritual and Moral Education of Student Youth" in the field of education. The article presents information about the perpetual importance of education for any period and society, highlighting recommendations based on national values in the spiritual and moral upbringing of youth.

Keywords: Education, spiritual and moral education, student-youth education, knowledge, virtues, maturity, the third Renaissance trend, spirituality, and knowledge.

Introduction

In the current process of globalization, it is a reality that serious efforts are being made everywhere in the world to promote human intellect and contemplation. This struggle, which takes place in various forms, requires each of us to critically assess the ongoing global processes and analyze the events occurring on the world stage with reason and thought. It is known that the decree of our esteemed President on "Additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational activities" dated May 3, 2019, the Uzbekistan Youth Forum on December 25, 2020, and the appeal to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 29, 2020, as well as the tasks set in the video conference on strengthening the cooperation of state and public organizations in improving the system of spiritual and educational work on January 19 of the current year are being implemented by the "Ma'rifat" Society of the Republic Center for Spiritual and Educational Work in collaboration with ministries, state, and public organizations.

The position emphasized by our state leader that "If the body of society's life is economy, its soul is spirituality," corresponds to the essence of Hazrat Navoi's call to harmony, and for our people, who entered the creation of the Third Renaissance wall with determination and enthusiasm, it once again

emphasizes that education, good manners, intellect, knowledge, spirituality, and spiritual sources are indispensable powers and sources of life for our society, where spirituality is the essence of life. Philosophically speaking, spirituality and knowledge have always been inexhaustible powers, bringing happiness, prosperity, peace, development, a field of mutual support, spiritual development, and elevation of the heart. Because they are based on high virtues, leading to the life of the nation, people, and individuals on the basis of ethical principles, avoiding the abyss of negligence, always striving for goodness, building this world, and flourishing in beauty.

As emphasized in the decree on "Additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational activities," our society, especially protecting youth from the threat of ignorance and organizing practical and scientific research activities based on new requirements, aims to strengthen the cooperation of state organizations, civil society institutions, public information outlets, and the private sector in this area. Solving existing problems requires raising the spirituality of youth, increasing the effectiveness and influence of spiritual and educational work, and creating a unified system to coordinate efforts to improve the moral and ethical competence of youth. In this regard, not only in our republic but also in the world education system, a method has been developed to improve the moral and ethical competence of youth, a mechanism for training competitive personnel, and an applied pedagogical system for developing the ethical qualities of youth have been implemented with interactive programs aligned with teaching models and technological advancements.

The "Declaration on Higher Education in the 21st Century" of the United Nations, as well as UNESCO's strategic documents on "Improving and Developing Higher Education," emphasize enhancing the quality of education in educational institutions globally, organizing modular education, and paying special attention to the methodology of educating students and youth in spiritual and moral values. Scientific research on developing youth's vocational integration, enhancing moral and ethical competence, and refining the methodology of social activity and initiative is actively underway in the global higher education system. In developed countries such as the United States, Russia, Germany, France, China, Korea, efforts are being made to enhance the thinking of students and youth, identify their talents early, and improve the effectiveness of mechanisms for spiritual and moral education through modular teaching, blended learning, master classes, and webinars.

In our country, various aspects of the spiritual and moral education process have been studied by many scholars, and possibilities for applying the results of these studies in the educational process have been recommended. Some of these studies, analyzing a specific aspect of the comprehensive spiritual and moral education process, suggest expanding the content of spiritual and moral education in the educational process and applying new methods in various courses, while others focus on research into issues of improving the system of educational work in educational institutions.

Development paths of using national values and foundations of national education in enhancing the process of spiritual and moral education, pedagogical foundations for shaping spiritual and moral culture, and the issue of spiritual and professional training of future specialists, especially in organizing an effective system of educational work in educational institutions, have been studied and analyzed by scholars such as V. Karimova, N. Dj. Mahmudova, O. Musurmonova, Sh. Sh. Olimov, M. Quronov, N. X. Oripova, Z. Q. Ismoilova, N. A. Muslimov, N. M. Ochilova, Y. P. Azarov, Z. E. Azimova.

The composition of spiritual and moral education, as a result of the formation of spiritual and moral knowledge in students, includes several ethical categories such as happiness, conscience, respect, justice, responsibility, love, kindness, dignity, belief, and loyalty. Students who have embraced spiritual and moral knowledge exhibit qualities such as initiative, social activity, patriotism, integrity, diligence, modesty, and loyalty. Young individuals possessing these virtues fulfill ethical requirements, and their national and universal values shape their spiritual heritage, traditions, and customs.

In conclusion, it is essential to emphasize that educating youth in spirituality, raising the younger generation based on national and universal values, and developing the spirituality and morality of the nation are crucial responsibilities for the state.

References:

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. For human dignity, his rights and freedoms, legal interests. -Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" 2022.
2. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Development strategy of new Uzbekistan. -Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" 2022.
3. Makhmudovna, A. Sh.(2022/1/5)The role of motivating lessons in teaching german as foreign language: TIPS AND IDEAS. Eurasian journal of academic research, (volume 1 issue9 2021 december)868,869,870

4. Makhmudovna, A. Sh.(2022/12/1). The role of brain in language learning and teaching. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 451-456
5. I.Karimov. High - spirituality is an unbeatable force. -Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" 2008.
6. 4. A.Avloni. Turkish culture or morals. Ziyouz.uz. 2012.
7. <https://religions.uz/news/detail?id=634>.
8. Siddikov, I., & Gulomov, A. (2020). Philosophical and psychological features of the formation of asertive behavior in the development of cognitive activity. In Психологическое здоровье населения как важный фактор обеспечения процветания общества (pp. 38-42).
9. Abdinazarovich, R. D., Abdullajonovna, Y. K., Ahadjanovich, Q. A., Bakhromovich, G. A., & Juraevna, N. N. (2020). The role of social service in the protection of human interests. Journal of Critical Reviews, 7(6), 1263-1267.
10. Gulomov, A. (2019). Participation and role of uzbekistan in finding solutions to global environmental problems. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 1(5), 152-156.

